

Some Aspects of Biochemical Synthesis.*

BY P. C. MITTER.

I wish to offer you my heartfelt thanks for the great honour you have done me by asking me to preside over the deliberations of this section and though fully aware of my own limitations, I venture to hope that with your good will and co-operation we may bring the session to a successful issue.

Before beginning my address, I wish to refer to the great loss which our science has suffered by the death of Prof. W. H. Perkin (jun.). Following in the footsteps of his illustrious father, Prof. Perkin incorporated in himself the highest and the best in the English School of Chemistry and the void which he has left will be difficult to fill.

I have chosen, as the subject of my address, "Some Aspects of Biochemical Synthesis."

Although a little over a hundred years have elapsed since Wöhler by his synthesis of urea demonstrated that vital products could be synthesised in the laboratory, the mechanism of the formation of these products is still shrouded in mystery. The small temperature and pressure range between which they are formed and the absence of the usual reagents heighten the mystery still further. Very little is known for instance about the formation of the starches, celluloses and the proteins, not to speak of the living protoplasm, which is one of the most important factors in biochemical synthesis.

The vital products might be compared to links in a long chain, of which only the end members are visible and probably also a little of the beginning. But there are frequent indications in the products themselves or in the substances with which they are associated, which give some clue as to their modes of formation in nature.

On a *priori* grounds, we may expect certain similarity between different classes of natural products, certain uniformity of design depending on similarity in the modes of their formation and as a matter of fact a

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close examination often reveals many points of resemblance between diverse classes of vital products. In products of the same class again certain distinct sub-classes are often met with. Thus, the researches of Willstätter and his pupils¹ have shown that the anthocyanins are derived from the three prototypes pelargonidine, cyanidine and delphinidine

Pelargonidine : $R=H, R'=H.$

Cyanidine : $R=H, R'=OH.$

Delphinidine : $R=OH, R'=OH.$

all of which contain in the position 4' of the phenyl radicle a free hydroxyl group. The hydroxyl group in the position 3 is linked with a sugar to from the anthocyanidin while the other hydroxyl groups are either free or blocked by methyl groups or form depside linkages with acids.

Similarly for the naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives found among plant products, the following empirical laws have been found to hold good².

(1) No naturally occurring anthraquinone derivative contains more than four substituent groups in the two benzene nuclei, namely, not more than *one* methyl (or carboxyl or carbinol group) which, if present, always occupies a β -position and not more than *three* hydroxyl groups.

(2) The substances containing the maximum number of substituents form the fundamental types and the other anthraquinone derivatives occurring in the same plant are all derived from this fundamental type, being either oxidation or reduction or etherification, etc., products of the same. The fundamental types are therefore also derivable by superposing the formulae of associated anthraquinones.

(3) Of the four substituents two (including the methyl or carboxyl or carbinol group, if present) occupy β -positions and the other two occupy α -positions.

(4) If both the β -substituents are in one ring the other groups also occur in the same ring or in other words, a homonuclear type is formed. If both the β -substituents are $\cdot OH$ groups they must occur in the same ring.

(5) If the β -substituents are in different rings the α -substituents are distributed in such a way as to produce a symmetrical configuration.

As no two types have three groups in common, it is possible by examining any one naturally occurring anthraquinone containing three substituents (sometimes even two substituents) to determine the fundamental type from which this particular substance and *all the other anthraquinone derivatives associated with it* have been derived.

Starting from anthraquinone we get, by substituting two β -positions by two hydroxyl groups or by one hydroxyl and one methyl group, the following types :—

From these four β -substituted products we can derive the four fundamental types of naturally occurring anthraquinones—two homonuclear and two heteronuclear.

Any theory of the formation of anthraquinone derivatives in nature must therefore explain not only the formation of the anthraquinone ring system but in such a scheme the hydroxyl and methyl groups (if any) must occur in their proper places in the ring system. So it is obvious that a theory on the basis of which we arrive at a substituted anthraquinone derivative containing a configuration of groups unlike any present in nature, cannot be regarded as a correct approximation to truth. The polyketide hypothesis of Collie³ suffers from this obvious drawback, although it offers a satisfactory explanation of the formation of the anthocyanine, cyanidine.

The task of the organic chemist, never an easy one, becomes particularly difficult in the case of those natural products which are not available in large quantities. The recognition of the fact, however, that nature seems to favour certain definite configuration of groups to the exclusion of others has often rendered an indirect method of determination of constitutions by previous synthesis and subsequent comparison and verification, possible.

The whole mass of internal evidence is in favour not of long chains owing their origin to cellulose material but of smaller units derived partly from this source, partly from the fragments of the protein molecules and partly from formaldehyde and its condensation products. Only with such small building units is it possible to explain the great diversity of types found among vital products.

The most satisfactory explanation of the formation of an anthraquinone ring system, for instance, appears to be by the fusion of a phenolic nucleus with a benzaldehyde or benzoic acid or a second phenolic or phenolic acid nucleus and formaldehyde followed by subsequent oxidation. We are strengthened in this supposition by the fact that there are numerous other vital products in which phenolic nuclei occur and these may, therefore, be regarded as among the fundamental building units.

Among lichen acids, we have substances like lecanoric acid and evernic acid consisting of two phenolic acid nuclei united together by the so-called depside linkage,

Lecanoric acid (R=H) ; Evernic acid (R=Me)

and some of the tannins contains such depsides linked with sugar molecules. Many of the anthocyanines again contain, besides the colouring matter proper with its phloroglucin component and the sugar radicles, a phenolic acid as a third constituent. As for instance, delphinine contains *p*-oxybenzoic acid and monardeine, *p*-oxycinnamic acid and this phenomenon according to Karrer⁴ establishes a relation between the anthocyanines and the depsides and tannins with which they are often associated in the plant.

Among the vital products there are numerous ketones, some like paeonol or fisetol being fat-aromatic, others like the oxybenzophenones being diaryl ketones. The first of these two classes of ketones forms the transition to chalcones, flavones, flavonols and anthocyanines and finally to the epicatechins, and Freudenberg⁵ has shown that these are all inter-related being members of an oxidation series.

Flavone : Luteolin.

Eriodictyol : Chalkone.

Flavanone : Butin.

Phloretin.

Closely allied to the flavones are the *isoflavones* like genistein⁶ which may be regarded as composed of a phenyl acetic acid nucleus, a phloroglucin nucleus and a formyl group. The first is also fairly well-distributed in nature and Gadamer⁷ has shown that the alkaloids of the *Chelidonium* group may be regarded as derived from *N*-methyl phenylethylamine with formaldehyde and phenylacetaldehyde, the phenylacetaldehyde and phenyl ethylamine being derived from phenylalanine:

There are other types in which two phenolic nuclei are united by a $-\text{CH}_2-$ group or by a ketonic group. An example of the first type is the lichen-product *albaspidin* investigated by Boehm⁸ which may be regarded as built up of phloroglucin, formaldehyde and butyraldehyde.^{8a}

Albaspidin.

The hydroxylated diaryl ketones either occur as such or in the form of their anhydrides, the xanthenes. From diaryl ketones there is a transition over 8-oxy-4-phenylchromanes to brazilin and haematoxylin

and it is curious to note that the carbinol group in brazilin and haematoxylin occupies the same position in the pyrone ring as the carbinol group in flavonols,⁹ anthocyanines and even in catechin.^{9a} In the laboratory a flavonol can be synthesised from a dihydric or trihydric phenol like resorcinol, or phloroglucinol, methoxyacetic acid and an aromatic acid¹⁰ and these are probably also the building units in the vital synthesis of flavonols. We should not be far wrong if we were to attribute to the carbinol group in flavonols, anthocyanidins, catechins and also perhaps in brazilin and haematoxylin, a common origin from a glycollic acid residue.

Among the phenol derivatives occurring among plant products, phloroglucin is easily the most widely distributed. The phloroglucin residue is found in oxybenzophenones like maclurin, xanthones (like gentisin) and it is fused with the γ -pyrone ring in most of the flavones and flavonols (even in an isoflavone like genistein,¹¹ in all the anthocyanines and also in catechin.

In a few cases, a resorcin residue is linked with the γ -pyrone ring, as for instance in fisetin and in the flavanone butin, while a tetrahydric phenol (oxidation product of phloroglucin) nucleus occurs in the flavones scutellarein¹² and baikalain¹³,

Scutellarein (R=OH)
Baikalein (R=H)

and the flavonol gossypetin¹⁴.

The second benzene nucleus in all the compounds mentioned above offers more variety and we have not only unsubstituted benzene nuclei (*e.g.* chrysin) but also hydroxyl groups in the position 2' (datisetin)¹⁵, 4' (apigenin), 2':4' (lotoflavin), 3':4' (quercetin) and 3':4':5' (myricetin).

Oxidation and reduction chains are very common in nature and it has been found for instance that all the anthraquinones of the chayroot and madder types can be arranged in the form of such oxidation and reduction chains.¹⁶

Among the flavones, flavonols and tannins also we meet with substances so related, occurring together

Quercetin, $R=OH$, $R'=OH$, $R''=H$;
 Kaempferol, $R=OH$, $R'=H$, $R''=H$;
 Kaempferid, $R=OCH_3$, $R'=H$, $R''=H$;
 Galangin, $R=H$, $R'=H$, $R''=H$;
 Gossypetin, $R=OH$, $R'=OH$, $R''=OH$.

as for instance quercetin and kaemferol, kaemferid and galangin, scutellarein and baikalein, gossypetin and quercetin, and quercetin with catechin and epicatechin. The simultaneous presence of gossypetin¹⁷ and quercetin in *Hibiscus sabdariffa* furnishes the necessary connecting link between phloroglucin and 1:2:3:5-tetraoxybenzene.

The observed close association in nature of allied substances in different stages of oxidation has often afforded valuable clues to the constitution of unknown substances. Thus from the fact that quercetin and catechin occur together, A. G. Perkin and Joshitake¹⁸ had inferred a formula for catechin which was verified by Freudenberg¹⁹ and his co-workers later on. From the fact that quebrachotannin is accompanied by fisetin and pistachiotannin by myricetin, they have predicted the formulas of some of the hypothetical catechins which are the mother substances of tannins.

Quebrachocatechin, R = H.

Pistachiocatechin, R = OH.

We see also that phloroglucin is one of the fundamental building units in vital synthesis forming, as it were, the keystone in the architecture of diverse classes of compound. Its progressive reduction would give resorcin and phenol and finally benzene and from phenol again by oxidation catechol and hydroquinone may be obtained. It is well-known that phenol may be oxidised by hydrogen peroxide to catechol and the simultaneous presence of substances, containing one a phenol and the other a catechol nucleus or one a phenol and another a benzene nucleus, point to a common origin for corresponding portions of the molecules.* The ease with which phloroglucin may be methylated in the ring accounts for the presence of the methylphloroglucin skeleton and its reduction product, the methylresorcin skeleton which is found in rubiadin and (in its oxidised form) in euxanthone and probably also in munjisthin.

* An example of peculiar biochemical interest is furnished by the pair, scutellarein baikalein, the former containing a phenolic nucleus being found in the leaves, while the latter containing an unsubstituted benzene ring occurs in the roots.

As regards phloroglucin, we can trace its origin to sugar which is the first product of carbon dioxide assimilation by the green plant. The bridge to the cyclic compounds is formed most probably by inositol which is very largely distributed in nature and which can be connected with phloroglucin by a simple relation :—

Inositol

Phloroglucin

The formation of a hydroaromatic compound from an aliphatic sugar has not been hitherto observed, nor the conversion of inositol to carbohydrates. The evidence of the relation between inositol and sugar is of an indirect character. Neuberger²⁰ has observed that by carefully heating inositol with phosphorus pentoxide, furfural, which has always been regarded as a true carbohydrate derivative, is obtained. Besides, the cycloses serve on the one hand as reserve material for the living organism and are on the other hand converted by bacterial action to open-chain compounds like propionic, butyric and lactic acids, thereby disclosing their biochemical relationship with the carbohydrates.²¹

As regards the pyrogallol nucleus, it may be regarded as derived from 1:2:3:5-tetraoxybenzene by reduction. It is not without interest that the root bark of *Fagara xanthoxyloides* Lam. *Rutacas* contains the substances bergapten and xanthotoxin,²² which have a common oxidation product.

Another fundamental unit in the formation of vital products is the isoprene unit. A critical examination by Ruzicka²³ has shown that the skeletons of members of the terpene family are formed by the regular union of isoprene units in a majority of cases and irregular in others. By regular union, Ruzicka means the union of isoprene units end to end, unlike ends being joined together and it must be conceded that the majority of terpenes possess such skeletal arrangements.

Myrcene and ocimene are both formed by the union of two isoprene units in such a way that the end carbon atom of the shortest chain of one unit, is attached to the end carbon atom of the longest chain of the other, the point of reference being the tertiary carbon atom.

TABLE II.

In the case of sesquiterpenes again we know the constitution of compounds formed on the A-B-A-B-A-B model like cadenene, eudesmol, etc., but compounds formed on the B-A-A-B-B-A model are probably not absent when we find a similar constitution in substances like santonine. Judging from analogy, we can expect to find among compounds formed by the union of four isoprene units representatives of the type A-B-A-B-A-B-A-B and B-A-B-A-B-A-B-A as well as of the types A-B-B-A-A-B-B-A and B-A-A-B-B-A-A-B, and abietic acid which according to Ruzicka is formed by an "irregular" union of isoprene units²⁵ will be probably found to belong to one of the latter categories. Rao and Simonsen²⁶ have thrown some doubts on the occurrence of sylvestrene in nature and referred among others to the "anomalous" position which sylvestrene occupies being "the only naturally occurring terpene derived from *m*-cymene, all the other members of the group being *p*-cymene derivatives."

We have seen already that the "anomaly", if any, is shared by at least two other natural products santene and santonine, the first of which is a terpene.

The absence of the characteristic colour reaction of sylvestrene in the oil from *Pinus sylvestris* need not surprise us when we consider that there are other substances in the mixture which also give colour reactions and the presence of which might disguise or inhibit the colour reaction due to pure sylvestrene. A curious error which might have influenced the views of the authors occurs in this paper. They observe: "It is not without significance that Atterberg^{26a} in one experiment could obtain only a dihydrochloride, m.p. 50° (the melting point of dipentene dihydrochloride) since it has been shown that in some cases Δ^4 -carene on treatment with hydrogen chloride yields dipentene dihydrochloride in larger quantity than sylvestrene dihydrochloride and the former therefore crystallises on cooling. What Atterberg says however is this:—

"Wie aus dem Obigen hervorgeht, ist das Sylvestren in Bezug zu den anderen bekannten Terpenen gut charakterisirt. Wie die anderen um

The alkaloids of the isoquinoline series like papaverine, narcotine, isothebaine, berberine, etc., possess in common a benzyl isoquinoline nucleus. The same primary structure, gives by the insertion of a lactone

ring between *a* and *d* the skeleton present in narcotine, while the formation of a link from *c* to *d* gives the nuclear structure present in isothebaine and potentially present in morphine, codeine, and thebaine. The insertion of a $-\text{CH}_2-$ bridge between *b* and *e* gives the nucleus present in berberine, while a $-\text{CHMe}-$ bridge gives the nucleus of the corydaline subgroup. From the former by a further step the characteristic central structure of the alkaloids

protopine and cryptopine can be derived.

Robinson²⁸ has elaborated a scheme which suggests reactions by which the alkaloids might have been synthesised in plants. It involves in addition to the ordinary processes of methylation, methylenation, reduction, oxidation and dehydration, two types of condensation to provide for the linking up of carbon to carbon, namely the aldol condensation and the condensation of carbinol-amines containing the group $=\text{C}(\text{OH})-\text{N}=\text{}$ with substances containing the group $=\text{CH}-\text{CO}-$.

The building units for the formation of alkaloids according to Robinson's scheme are the amines and amino-acids derived from the hydrolysis of proteins.

Haworth²⁹ has drawn attention to the intimate connection that appears to exist between the skeletal structure of the sugars and some of the amino-acids. "It is very probable", writes Haworth, "that there exists a direct relationship between the carbohydrates and the proteins and it appears clear according to the following analogies that these two groups, the most important of organic derivatives, possess a common origin.

The connection of glucose with coniine, pelletierine, ψ -pelletierine and isopelletierine in which the lateral chain of glucose is probably condensed with acetaldehyde or with a triose is an example. Similarly in the case of the alkaloids of the pyrrol group like stachydrin, betonicine etc. the lateral side chain of xylose is apparent.

There are other types of biochemical transformation of glucose, as for instance its conversion to a pyrone derivative kojic acid by the action of *Aspergillus oryzae*³⁰. Besides, one of the products obtained by heating malt is α -methyl- β -hydroxy- γ -pyrone, maltol.

We see, therefore, that the units with which Nature synthesises her products are largely derived from the sugars or from the proteins at least some of which in their turn are derivable from the sugars, specially the hexoses and pentoses and it is easy to understand that there would be a tendency to exaggerate their importance. For instance, the methyl pentoses, which are fairly well represented in nature have been regarded as being formed not as primary products of biochemical synthesis but as secondary products derived from the hexoses by the reduction³¹ of the terminal $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ group to a $-\text{CH}_3$ group. Votoček³² has pointed difficulties attendant on such a point of view. If the pentoses were formed from the corresponding hexoses, by a reduction process of this type, isorhodoose which corresponds to glucose would have been one of the commonest of methyl pentoses. On the other hand, fucose which is actually so largely distributed in nature would have been rare, since the hexose from which it is derivable by reduction namely *l*-galactose is extremely rare in the vegetable kingdom. To obviate these difficulties Votoček suggests that we should seek the source of the methyl pentoses in the condensation of aldehydes containing methyl groups like acetaldehyde or perhaps lactic aldehyde with formic or glycollic or glyceric aldehyde.

In a recent communication, Robinson³³ has further elaborated a scheme indicating the relationship of some complex natural products to the sugars and amino-acids and pointed out *inter alia* that the ornithine skeleton is also present in histidine, the lysine in quinine while nicotine

contains both ornithine and lysine skeletons. Harmaline and physostigmine can both be derived from the amino-acid tryptophane, while in chlorophyll and haemin the sugar skeletons are perceptible.

We see, therefore, that the conditions prevailing in nature favour the formation of certain distinct classes of compounds, having common frameworks and that there are sub-classes within these classes, which differ from one another in the number and disposition of substituent groups.

The vital products belonging to different classes are sometimes related in such a way as to mark stages in development; and when, as is often the case, such substances occur together, they offer valuable clues as to the course of the biochemical synthesis.

The building units in vital syntheses are derived partly from formaldehyde and its condensation or alteration products, chiefly the sugars and partly from the amino-acids (some of which are themselves derivable from the sugars) which are the products of protein hydrolysis, "the molecular debris, strewing the path of enzyme action."

The whole mass of internal evidence is in favour of comparatively small building units, without assuming which it is difficult to explain the great variety of types that are met with in nature.

Diverse products are formed in the living organism, some as the result of the anabolic, others again of the catabolic processes taking place in it and these again suffer various secondary changes like oxidation, reduction methylation, methylenation, hydrolysis and aldol and carbinol-amine condensations giving rise to the various kaleidoscopic patterns with which nature greets our eyes or delights our senses.

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